

Silent Epistemology: Embodied Intersubjectivity in Zazen

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Nicholas J Watkins

University of Bristol
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Han (板), struck by the Shuso, marking the beginning and end of zazen. A sonic threshold that came to anchor my fieldwork on silence.

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Author's Declaration

I declare that the work in this dissertation was carried out in accordance with the requirements of the University's Regulations and Code of Practice for Taught Programmes and that it has not been submitted for any other academic award. Except where indicated by specific reference in the text, this work is my own work. I have identified all material in this dissertation which is not my own work through appropriate referencing and acknowledgement. Where I have quoted or otherwise incorporated material, which is the work of others, I have included the source in the references. Any views expressed in the dissertation, other than referenced material, are those of the author.

Abstract

Silence is often treated as a communicative void, a suspension of meaning, or a disruption of social connection. This dissertation challenges that assumption through an ethnographic study of zazen (seated meditation) at the Bristol Zen Dojo, where silence is not the absence of sociality but its medium. Through sensory ethnography and phenomenological analysis, the findings reveal that shared silence in zazen produces a paradoxical form of intimacy: practitioners report feeling *alone together*, connected through stillness rather than dialogue. Identity is not asserted but softened - formed relationally through posture, discipline, and affective synchrony. Through this investigation of non-verbal dimensions of sociality, this research identifies what I term a *silent epistemology*: a mode of knowing grounded in somatic attention and atmospheric attunement. While Pagis (2010) identifies *silent intersubjectivity* within Vipassanā meditation, examining how practitioners maintain social connections in silence, this study reveals how silence functions as a generative medium for knowledge transmission and creation. Additional themes include the transformation of temporal perception during silent meditation, the enduring impact of silence beyond the dojo, and the distinctive challenges faced by newcomers. In foregrounding silence as a site of knowledge and co-presence, this research invites a reconsideration of anthropological and broader social scientific assumptions about communication, sociality, and the nature of knowing.

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1. Introduction

Silence. A pervasive yet often elusive feature of social life. In many social theories, silence is often framed as absence, concealment, or exclusion, marking moments when speech falters, is withheld, or forcibly denied (Das, 2007; Spivak, 1988; Zerubavel, 2006). These analyses have been essential in examining silence as symptomatic of trauma, marginalisation, and systemic violence. Recent scholarship has begun to reframe silence not as a lack, but as a generative phenomenon (Cassaniti, 2024; Dragojlovic & Samuels, 2021; Pagis, 2010, 2019).

While many religious traditions valorise silence as a vehicle for spiritual cultivation or communion with the sacred, Zen accords it a distinctive ontological and epistemological status. In *zazen*¹, silence is not merely the absence of speech but an intersubjective and atmospheric form of practice that nurtures a dissolution of individual identity, which paradoxically, can enable a relational coherence or affective synchrony between meditators. This process is not framed as a linear transformation, but as clarification: a stripping away of habitual conditioning to allow for direct presence. In Zen terms, this is *kenshō* - the realisation of one's original nature through non-grasping awareness (Bielefeldt, 1988, p. 76). While Buddhist traditions treat silence as ethically and spiritually vital, Anglophone scholarship often reads it as rupture or dysfunction, reflecting logocentric assumptions.

In response, this thesis asks:

1. How does silence facilitate intersubjective experience among *zazen* practitioners within a shared meditation space?
2. How does silence contribute to the emergence of relational identity through embodied practice in *zazen*?
3. How might ethnographic engagement with contemplative silence challenge and expand understandings of sociality beyond logocentric frameworks?

To address these questions, I draw upon fieldwork conducted at the Bristol Zen Dojo (BZD), combining questionnaires and in-depth interviews with sensory ethnography. This approach

¹ *Zazen*, the seated meditation practice central to Sōtō Zen - a Japanese lineage of Mahāyāna Buddhism grounded in the writings of 13th-century monk Eihei Dōgen - is not dependent on the “mental abilities” of the meditator, as stated in his meditation manual, the *Fukan Zazengi* (Bielefeldt, 1988, p. 145).

enabled examination of both practitioners' verbal reflections and the embodied, sensory dimensions of zazen. By investigating silence as both concept and lived experience, I analyse how it bridges intersubjective connection within this community.

This dissertation argues that silence in zazen functions as a generative, intersubjective phenomenon that reveals a fundamental paradox: as practitioners surrender individual identity through embodied stillness, they simultaneously develop deeper relational coherence - what might be called a shared identity of no-self. Building on this insight, I propose a '*silent epistemology*' that recognises how embodied attunement² creates fields of shared presence, challenging Western understandings of sociality. This research contributes to scholarship that reframes silence as active and constitutive rather than passive or marginal.

2. Literature Review

This literature review is structured in five parts. First, I examine influential interpretations of silence as a mechanism of power and oppression. Second, I consider how logocentric biases have shaped understandings of silence in Western contexts, contrasting these with more diverse cross-cultural approaches. Third, I explore phenomenological frameworks of embodied intersubjectivity that provide theoretical resources for reconceptualising silence as a constitutive dimension of social life. Fourth, I explore how silence functions across various contemplative traditions, with particular attention to recent anthropological engagements with silent practice. Finally, I examine the distinctive approach to silence within Zen Buddhism, focusing on its non-instrumental framing.

2.1 Silence as Power and Oppression

A significant body of feminist, sociological, and postcolonial scholarship has examined silence as a mechanism of control and subjugation, particularly in relation to gendered, racialised, and colonial hierarchies. Feminist theorists often frame silence as a product of patriarchal constraint, with speech positioned as a route to emancipation (Behar, 1996; Jule, 2004).

² Embodied attunement refers to the process through which practitioners develop a bodily sensitivity to shared atmospheric fields and intersubjective experiences. It builds on Csordas's (1993) "somatic modes of attention," and connects to theoretical work on atmospheric attunement (Stewart, 2011) and phenomenological approaches to intersubjectivity (Jackson, 1996; Merleau-Ponty, [1945] 2012).

Postcolonial scholars, meanwhile, emphasise the ethical imperative to “let the subaltern speak” (Spivak, 1988), interrogating the systemic silencing of marginalised groups. Across these perspectives, silence is positioned not as a neutral absence, but as fundamentally oppositional to autonomy and self-expression, reinforcing its association with complicity, repression, or erasure.

This understanding is extended through the concept of 'conspiratorial silence', which foregrounds the collective nature of non-disclosure. Simmel (1906), in his foundational text, was among the first to examine how silence sustains social cohesion through concealment. Eviatar Zerubavel (2006), in *The Elephant in the Room: Silence and Denial in Everyday Life*, turns to the micro-politics of denial, showing how everyday silences obscure discomfort and defer acknowledgment. While these silences are often shared, their function, according to Zerubavel, is to preserve social order by evading confrontation. One particularly devastating example is the societal silence surrounding sexual abuse, which he argues deepens victims' isolation: “the intense feelings of loneliness often experienced by incest and rape victims are largely a product of such conspiracies of silence” (Zerubavel, 2006, p.16). In such contexts, silence becomes a vehicle of psychological harm, undermining trust and foreclosing the possibility of relational repair.

2.2 Beyond Logocentrism

This enduring association of silence with dysfunction, in part, stems from Western logocentrism, which privileges speech as the primary site of meaning (Derrida, 1976) and is reinforced by psychoanalytic models that cast verbal expression as essential to psychic health (Foucault, 1978). Mann (1967, p.15) epitomises this view: "speech is civilisation itself. The word, even the most contradictory word, preserves contact - it is silence which isolates." This logocentrism is particularly pronounced in Anglo-American contexts, which Glenn (2004, p.18) critiques as characteristic of our “talky culture.” These high-velocity verbal exchange norms create distinctive interactional patterns. As Deborah Tannen (1985, p.104) documented, New Yorkers often did not register their own unacknowledged comments as problematic, whereas participants from other regions in her study expressed that if their comments during conversation were ignored, it was typically received as rudeness - sometimes generating disorientating affect. Similarly, Jarowski (1993 p.6) observes that people "accelerate conversations and avoid pauses at all costs", as silence is interpreted as indicating "lack of

mutual rapport between interlocutors." Such interpretive tendencies reflect a broader cultural logic in which silence creates distance between participants, threatening the intersubjective space that speech ostensibly maintains (Gurevitch, 1989).

However, this preference for speech over silence is not exclusive to Western contexts. Tannen's (1985) synthesis showed that silence also signals disrespect among the Igbo of Nigeria - where greetings are essential to affirming social ties - while Italian-American and New York Jewish communities similarly tend to express warmth and attentiveness through verbal immediacy. Though manifesting in culturally distinct ways, these examples illustrate how the prioritisation of speech over silence extends across diverse cultural settings, each with its own social logic and interactional norms.

In contrast to speech-dominant communication paradigms, various cultural systems regard silence as an intentional mode of interaction. Japanese communicative practices exemplify this approach, where silence functions as a deliberate strategy for social harmony, respect, and interpersonal sensitivity. Lebra (1976) and Nakane (2007) examine the relational and ethical dimensions of Japanese silence - Lebra, contextualising it within broader norms of implicitness and conflict avoidance, while Nakane's intercultural studies show how silence enables subtle alignment between speakers. Rather than indicating passivity, silence emerges as a cultivated form of responsiveness. Similarly, Finnish communicative culture, as Petkova (2015) demonstrates, interprets silence as embodying valued cultural principles of privacy, emotional restraint, and attentiveness.

What unifies these diverse examples is not a shared valuation of either silence or speech, but recognition that both are always embedded in social contexts, patterned by cultural norms, and imbued with relational significance. As Tannen (1985, p.106) observes, even within Anglo-American settings, communicative expectations vary, where some speakers may "risk saying too little" out of a culturally embedded ethic of considerateness, revealing silence to be socially complex and morally inflected.

2.3 Embodied Intersubjectivity

While cultural attitudes toward silence vary considerably as discussed above, anthropological theory itself has often reflected logocentric biases. Despite the radical interrogation of ethnographic authority during the Writing Culture debates of the 1980s, these critiques

remained focused on voice, text, and representation, leaving silence largely untheorised (Clifford & Marcus, 1986). It was not until the embodied and sensory turns of the 1990s and 2000s that non-discursive dimensions of experience - such as bodily sensation, affect, and atmospheric attunement - were foregrounded as central analytic concerns in anthropology. Scholars such as Thomas Csordas (1990), Steven Feld (1996), David Howes (2003), and Sarah Pink ([2009] 2015) played key roles in reorienting ethnographic attention toward the body, the senses, and the affective qualities of lived environments.

The phenomenological turn provided the conceptual foundation for these shifts. Anthropologists working on embodiment and intersubjectivity drew increasingly on phenomenological thinkers, most notably Merleau-Ponty's ([1945] 2012) account of the lived body as the ground of perception. His work repositioned the body as the basis through which the world is experienced, not simply as an object in space, but a sensing, acting subject entangled in a field of relations with others. This orientation informed Csordas's (1994) proposal of embodiment as the existential ground of culture, arguing that the body is the locus of perception and intersubjective engagement. This reframing enabled a shift away from mere representational models of knowledge. Extending this, Michael Jackson (1996) advanced a relational conception of intersubjectivity that redirects attention from internalised, bounded experience to the unfolding dynamics between persons. Drawing on Ricoeur (1979, p.127), Jackson emphasises that meaning emerges within the lived immediacy of encounter, prior to theoretical or linguistic codification.

This phenomenological orientation has been enriched by theoretical work on affective atmospheres. Building on Merleau-Ponty's insights, scholars have explored how shared spaces become infused with qualities that shape collective experience. Hermann Schmitz's neo-phenomenological approach conceptualises atmospheres as spatially extended affective fields that precede individual subjectivity (Schmitz et al., 2011). Stewart (2011) examines how atmospheric attunements shape collective experience through subtle modes of alignment and resonance. Eisenlohr (2023) applies these insights to ritual contexts, exploring how atmospheric qualities in religious settings actively shape how practices are felt and perceived, complementing Csordas's (1993, p.138) *somatic modes of attention* that illuminates how embodied practices create fields of shared affect that simultaneously transcend individual experience while intensifying bodily presence.

These theoretical developments provide crucial resources for reconceptualising silence not as the negation of communication, but as a vital dimension of relationality. Intersubjectivity, therefore, emerges through the immediacy of *being-with-others* (Jackson, 1996, p.16), a process particularly evident in shared contemplative practices where silence becomes a generative condition.

2.4 Silence as a Constitutive Force

If the sensory and phenomenological turns have challenged anthropology to take embodiment and intersubjectivity seriously, contemplative practices invite us to consider silence not only as a site of experience but as a condition of being. Across diverse religious contexts, practitioners cultivate a silence that Dauenhauer (1980, p.3) argues is a "nonderivative silence which is both positive and complex." He further proposes that silence is at least "equiprimordial" with speech, that is, equally fundamental to the human condition (ibid, p.3). In this view, silence is not what follows speech, or what speech fails to fill; rather, it is a parallel mode of relationality - of being-in-the-world, through which meaning, connection, and perception are actively constituted.

2.4.1 Cross-Traditional Perspectives

This understanding of silence is reflected in its central role within a broad array of contemplative traditions throughout history. Christian monastic traditions such as the Benedictine and Carthusian orders have long cultivated silence as a spiritual discipline. St. Benedict's Rule establishes *taciturnitas* (restraint of speech) as essential to contemplative life (Casey, 2005). Quaker worship centres on collective silence as a fundamental mode through which participants seek to discern what they term the 'Inner Light', establishing a communal spiritual practice built on shared stillness rather than speech (Bauman, 1985). In Hindu traditions, *mauna* (the vow of silence) functions as both ascetic practice and epistemological method, particularly within Advaita Vedānta (Sharma, 2004). Similarly, in Sufism, silence is cultivated as a means of inner purification and receptivity to the divine (Schimmel, 1975).

2.4.2 Anthropological Engagements with Silence in Buddhist Contexts

Recent anthropological approaches have been particularly valuable in documenting how silence functions as an embodied, inter-relational practice rather than merely an absence of speech. Michal Pagis (2009) provides a foundational contribution through her theoretical framework of *embodied self-reflexivity*, which she further develops in ethnographic studies of Vipassanā³ meditation communities in Israel and the United States (2010; 2019). Rather than conceptualising introspection as a purely cognitive process, Pagis demonstrates how meditative silence enables practitioners to cultivate awareness through bodily sensation, generating a form of reflexivity that emerges in the absence of linguistic mediation. In her 2010 study, she challenges assumptions that silence impedes sociality, arguing instead that meditation involves covert mechanisms of “silent intersubjectivity”, demanding new ethnographic attention to how relationality is enacted through “embodied involvement” (Pagis, 2010, p.3, 25).

Julia Cassaniti (2024) explores silence as a persuasive mechanism within Thai Buddhist meditation practices. Through ethnographic research at Wat Pradhatu Sri Chom Thong Voravihan in Northern Thailand, Cassaniti identifies three distinct ways in which silence generates persuasive effects within meditation retreats: first, silence operates in contrastive relation to speech, gaining its power through this juxtaposition; second, silence functions symbolically as an expression of moral personhood within Thai Buddhist contexts; and third, silence facilitates interpersonal corporeal attunement among practitioners. Cassaniti's analysis is particularly significant in its emphasis on the corporeal dimension of silence, arguing that in Thai meditation practices, silence works through the body to transform intersubjective space. This perspective moves beyond examining silence merely for its outcomes and instead approaches it as a disciplinary practice itself. Moreover, she suggests that such religious forms of silent persuasion constitute a powerful force for navigating broader sociopolitical life beyond ritual settings.

2.5 Temporal Dimensions of Contemplative Silence

The temporal dimensions of contemplative silence offer another important framework for understanding its constitutive role in shaping lived experience. In a neurophenomenological

³ Vipassanā meditation is a Theravadā Buddhist meditation that is popular in SouthEast Asia and around the world.

study of long-term mindfulness practitioners, Berkovich-Ohana et al. (2013) found that states described as “timeless” and “spaceless” were accompanied by altered neural activity, particularly in regions associated with bodily awareness. These findings suggest that meditative silence is not merely introspective but entails a shift in the felt structure of time itself - one that emerges through embodied, non-verbal awareness. To make sense of such experiential shifts, Henri Bergson’s (1913) notion of *durée réelle* (real duration) offers a valuable theoretical frame. While Bergson does not address meditation directly, his distinction between segmented clock-time and lived, qualitative duration is particularly helpful in showing how silence can suspend chronological flow in favour of a continuous, immersive present. From this perspective, contemplative silence may not only reshape bodily awareness but reconstitute temporal perception at a fundamental level.

2.6 Silence in Zen Buddhism

Zen Buddhism offers a particularly distinctive formulation of silence, one that challenges the idea of silence as absence or preparatory condition. Within the Sōtō Zen lineage, the practice of zazen is not positioned as a means to enlightenment, but as its direct and immediate expression (Leighton, 2007). This emphasis is most clearly articulated by Eihei Dōgen, who wrote: “sitting in zazen is not learning Zen concentration. It is simply the peaceful and joyful gate of Dharma⁴”, where rather than striving toward spiritual attainment, zazen expresses Buddha-nature itself through silence and posture (Dōgen, trans. Nishijima & Cross, 2007, p.364; Loy, 1985).

David Preston (1988) and Dale Wright (1998; 2008) offer complementary insights into the experience and interpretation of Zen practice. Preston draws on phenomenological sociology to explore how beginners come to inhabit the embodied form of zazen using Sudnow’s (1979) study - examining embodied skill acquisition through jazz piano training to frame meditation as a gradual realignment of perception through bodily discipline. His account resists cognition-heavy models, showing how intersubjectivity arises through gesture, posture, and repeated engagement. Wright, meanwhile, adopts a hermeneutic approach to classical Zen texts. In his reading of Zen Master Huang Po, he examines his teaching: “Mind has been transmitted with

⁴ In Zen Buddhism, Dharma means the nature of reality, and the path of practice. It refers both to the teachings and to the direct experience of awakening. When teachers speak of Dharma transmission, they mean passing on this awakened understanding - not through words, but through shared presence and insight between teacher and student (Heine, 2023).

Mind, and these minds have been identical” (Wright, 1998, p.146), but stresses how it is immediately undercut by the follow-up: “Mind is not Mind and transmission is not really transmission” (Ibid, p. 146). For Wright, this tension exemplifies how Zen transmission resists fixed meaning, and how interpreters like John Blofeld impose metaphysical clarity that the texts themselves may disrupt. Together, Preston and Wright show both the embodied learning of Zen and the contested nature of its textual authority.

While their approaches focus on either the bodily uptake of practice or the interpretive framing of texts, Zen also offers internal frameworks that challenge dualistic distinctions between communication and silence. The concept of *ishin-denshin* (以心伝心), often translated as 'communication without words,' suggests that knowledge is transmitted directly from mind-to-mind, beyond verbal articulation (Bielefeldt, 1988, p.5). Heine (2023, p.48) further develops these ideas through his examination of Dharma transmission in Sōtō Zen, particularly in Dōgen's teachings as “fully embodied.” For Dōgen, transmission emerges not through mystical means but through disciplined presence, embodied practice, and relational intimacy cultivated within both teacher-student dynamics and the broader sangha (community) (ibid).

This communal dimension of practice manifests as a form of non-dual awareness that David Loy (1985, p. 73) describes as *wu-wei* or "the action of nonaction" - a state of purposeless yet generative presence. While originating in Daoist philosophy, this concept illuminates Zen's approach to meditation as effortless attention. In zazen, practitioners cultivate this quality not through wilful concentration but through what Loy (1985, p. 76) clarifies as simply "letting-be", allowing thoughts and sensations to arise and pass without fixation. This paradoxical approach to practice - effort directed toward non-effort - constitutes a distinctive stance toward silence, one that seeks not to *achieve* tranquillity or a ‘desired state’ but to *uncover* the inherent stillness already present beneath discursive thought.

While scholars have explored both philosophical dimensions of Zen concepts and the social organisation of Zen communities (e.g. Preston, 1988; Wright, 1998; 2008), the embodied, experiential quality of shared silence in zazen practice remains understudied, despite important contributions from anthropologists studying silent meditation in other Buddhist contexts⁵ (e.g.

⁵ Pagis (2010, 2019) studied Vipassanā in the tradition taught by S.N. Goenka, characterised by its strict structure and emphasis on body scanning. Cassaniti's (2024) study also examined Vipassanā principles but in the tradition of Mahasi Sayadaw as adapted by Ajahn Thong, with greater emphasis on noting and mindfulness.

Pagis's work on Vipassanā, 2010; Cassaniti's research on Thai Buddhist meditation, 2024). Moreover, as Komjathy (2018, p.4-8) writes, much of contemplative studies remains framed by individual cognition and scientific abstraction, often overlooking the relational, embedded nature of practice. This study addresses these gaps by extending Pagis and Cassaniti's insights into intersubjective silence through full immersion within Sōtō Zen practice at the BZD, exploring how contemplative silence facilitates intersubjective experience beyond verbal language.

3. Methodology

3.1 A 'Mixed Methods' Approach

This study followed a triangulated mixed methods design (Creswell & Clark, 2018), incorporating participant observation, questionnaires, and semi-structured interviews in overlapping phases. Data collection began with sustained participant observation across 58 evening and 11 sunrise sessions. Detailed fieldnotes were recorded after each, forming a key part of the analysis (see 3.4). Observation was grounded in sensory ethnography (Pink, 2015), with attention grounded in the dojo's sonic environment and affective atmospheres. The questionnaire included Likert-type items (Boone & Boone, 2012) and open prompts, enabling participants to provide both scaled responses and narrative reflections. This was followed by semi-structured interviews, designed to complement the questionnaire by inviting deeper reflection of zazen experience. Although all strands contributed to analysis, the study was qualitatively weighted overall (Flick, 2014), and findings integrated across methods to produce a layered, cross-validated interpretation (see *Figure 1*).

Figure 1. A chart showing the mixed methods approach. The triangulated design (Creswell & Clark, 2018) combined questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, and ongoing sensory ethnographic fieldwork (Pink, 2015). These strands were analysed in combination to develop interpretive themes.

3.2 Questionnaire and Ethical Reflection

Rather than using pre-existing instruments, I created a custom-designed questionnaire tailored to the particularities of zazen practice, in line with Flick’s (2014, p.38) view that qualitative methods should be adapted to the complexity and context of the subject under study. The process of designing the questionnaire was guided by preliminary observations during early field visits and informed by themes emerging during informal conversations with practitioners. While Bernard (2011, p.256) discusses ‘pretesting’ primarily in relation to interview schedules, the same rationale supports its use in designing questionnaires. To this end, I conducted an informal pilot with 2 ordained attendees, whose feedback helped ensure that the tone and content were appropriate across varying levels of experience. The participant group consisted of 2 newcomers, 3 returning students, 5 ordained practitioners, and 2 priests. These positional categories are also reflected in the spatial seating arrangement shown in *Figure 2*. The questionnaire also included specific demographic items to support later comparative analysis, detailed in 4.1.

Figure 2. A diagram representing the spatial layout of the BZD during zazen⁶. While attendance varied between sessions, the orientation and general seating arrangement remained consistent. This spatial constancy, recorded through repeated field observations and aided by memory, was significant to the atmosphere of practice and shaped how silence was experienced in relation to others.

Recruitment developed organically through a poster⁷ placed on the dojo notice board, group chat announcements, and priest-led introductions for newcomers - but also through my ongoing presence. Trust was built gradually, through zazen and informal conversations, allowing interest to emerge relationally. The questionnaire⁸ comprised 30 items across 6 sections. These combined narrative prompts with Likert-type items rated on a 1-10 scale from ‘Strongly Disagree’ to ‘Strongly Agree,’ allowing for both qualitative insight and response comparability. Prior to the findings, I obtained verbal permission from the priests to carry out this research. All participants were provided with a participant information sheet and consent

⁶ Shuso, a senior practitioner who takes on leadership responsibilities during practice, supporting the teachers and the community.

⁷ See Appendix A for the recruitment poster.

⁸ See Appendix B for the questionnaire.

form⁹ at the point of questionnaire distribution. These documents outlined the study's purpose, voluntary participation, and data protection measures.

Participants were given the opportunity to ask questions and withdraw at any time. Completed questionnaires were anonymised and stored securely in a physical folder, with any digital responses encrypted and uploaded to the University of Bristol's OneDrive. Consent forms were stored separately from participant data to align with data protection procedures. No vulnerable individuals or persons under the age of 18 were included in the study. This research adhered to the ASA Ethical Guidelines (Association of Social Anthropologists, 2021) throughout the entire process.

3.3 Interviewing

I conducted 12 semi-structured interviews¹⁰, only with participants who had completed the questionnaire - following ethical procedures outlined during questionnaire distribution. Each interview lasted approximately 1 hour, with 2 interviews lasting nearly 2 hours. Most were face-to-face within the dojo following zazen - although a small number took place on non-practice days or online to accommodate participant availability. Considering Hammersley and Atkinson's (2019, p.154) caution that recording technologies can be disruptive in certain ethnographic environments, I chose to rely on contemporaneous notetaking. Where responses were particularly affective or conceptually significant, I documented participants' words verbatim. The sample size was guided by Guest et al. (2006), who suggest that data saturation is often reached within 12 interviews, particularly within focused, context-specific groups such as this.

The interview sequence opened with an expert interview with one of the priests. As described by Bogner and Menz (2009), expert interviews can serve an exploratory function, providing structured yet flexible access to specialised, field-specific knowledge at an early stage, allowing for deeper reflection on the ritual, ethical, and pedagogical roles of silence. Following Hammersley and Atkinson's (2019, p.112) consideration that the line between participant

⁹ See Appendix C for the participant information sheet and consent form.

¹⁰ See Appendix D for the general set of interview questions; a separate expert interview schedule was used for the priests, provided in Appendix E.

observation and interviewing is often blurred in ethnographic work, my approach integrated formal interviews with the everyday rhythms of practice.

3.4 Participant Observation

Participant observation was central to this study and grounded in a sensory ethnographic approach (Pink, 2015). My presence in the dojo extended beyond formal data collection of zazen to involve shared meals, informal conversations, and time spent observing the rhythms of place. These spontaneous interactions formed part of a broader oral landscape that enriched the fieldwork. Rather than treating data collection as a series of discrete, extractive episodes, I remained open to reflections that surfaced organically, in ways that were context-sensitive and minimally intrusive. Moreover, rather than acting as an external observer, I sought to be bodily and affectively attuned - multisensorially - to the atmosphere, particularly where subtle gestures held meaning beyond words.

Following Pink's (2015, ch.4) emphasis on *sensory emplaced learning*, I treated observation as a situated, relational process. Spatial constancy, such as the consistent seating arrangement (see Figure 2), became a key site of attention, shaping how I experienced and later interpreted the co-presence of bodies in silence. These insights emerged through a combination of my own multisensory presence, memory, and fieldnotes recorded immediately after each session. Rather than isolating observation from other methods, I approached it as an ongoing mode of engagement that further informed both the questionnaire and interview design. The blurred line between participation and observation became a strength, unfolding predominantly in real time.

3.5 Analysis

Findings from fieldnotes, questionnaires, and interviews underwent thematic analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2006) inductive approach. First, I conducted initial coding of all textual materials, identifying recurring terms, metaphors, and descriptions across participant accounts. These codes were organised into preliminary categories related to silence experience. Second, I performed cross-method triangulation, systematically comparing patterns identified in questionnaire responses against both interview transcripts and fieldnotes to establish analytical consistency. Finally, these validated patterns were interpreted through theoretical frameworks including Pink's (2015) sensory ethnography, Csordas's (1990) embodiment

paradigm, and Eisenlohr's (2023) atmospheric analytics. While my embodied field experience sensitised me to particular dimensions of zazen practice, the analytical work maintained methodological rigor through systematic coding procedures, triangulation across data sources, and team review of emerging interpretations. This approach ensured that while participant observation provided essential contextual understanding, analysis was conducted through documented, transparent procedures rather than relying solely on my embodied knowledge. Themes emerged from this systematic process rather than from impressionistic readings, with particular attention to how participants' accounts converged or diverged from observed practice across different positionalities within the dojo community.

3.6 Researcher Positionality

My role as a researcher was shaped by prior experience with meditation and a personal familiarity with silence as a meaningful presence. Although not an insider to the BZD community, I entered this research with brief experience of zazen in Japan and other meditative practices internationally, including silent retreats. This background shaped an embodied sensitivity to the atmosphere of collective silence, especially within religious contexts, influencing how I moved through the field and listened to what was shared - verbally or otherwise. I was also informed by anthropological work that treats silence as relational and embodied. Pagis's (2010, 2019) research on Vipassanā complicates the idea of meditation as solitary introspection, showing how silence can cultivate intersubjective awareness. Cassaniti's (2015) study of Thai monastic retreats similarly reveals silence as a persuasive force that reconfigures interpersonal space through presence and discipline. These works not only deepened my interest but helped attune me to silence as an affective and generative phenomenon.

While I aimed to remain open and reflexive, I recognise that my interpretations were inevitably informed not only by my own bodily presence and meditative history, but also by prior scholarly engagements. At the same time, my position as a researcher with meditative experience may have influenced how participants perceived me and shaped their willingness to speak openly. Some may have withheld certain views, assuming I already understood or shared their perspective, while others may have been drawn to speak with me because of a perceived affinity. These dynamics potentially skewed participation and the types of narratives that were shared. My visible presence during sits and shared meals may also have subtly

influenced the atmosphere I was observing. These limitations do not invalidate the findings, but they do show the situated, co-produced nature of ethnographic knowledge and the need to remain attuned to who speaks, who stays silent, and under what conditions.

4. Results and Discussion

The following analysis draws on findings collected from 12 participants through structured questionnaires, semi-structured interviews, and sensory ethnographic fieldnotes at the BZD¹¹. The study generated both quantitative data from Likert-scale questionnaire items and qualitative narratives, with primary emphasis placed on the latter alongside embodied sensory observations.

4.1 Contextual Overview

4.1.1 Thematic Structure

Six major experiential themes emerged from this integrated analysis: (1) intersubjective paradox of connection in silence, (2) identity formation through shared silence (3) altered perceptions of time during zazen (4) impacts of silence beyond meditation contexts, (5) the distinctive experiences of newcomers, and (6) the developmental trajectory of embodied attunement as a unifying thread across these domains. While some themes correspond directly to the research questions, others were shaped by participants' narratives and recurring patterns in fieldnote observations. Additionally, expert interviews revealed the emergence of the previously mentioned concept of 'silent epistemology' - a mode of knowing grounded in embodied, relational silence drawing from the Japanese concept *ishin-denshin*, which I develop as a theoretical contribution in 4.8.

4.1.2 Participant Demographics

Participants represented a range of experience levels: 2 newcomers attending their first session, 3 returning practitioners (1-2 years' experience), 5 ordained practitioners (11 months - 7+

¹¹ At the BZD, evening zazen consists of two 20-minute sessions separated by 5 minutes of *kinhin* (walking meditation where each step is synchronised with the breath and attention is placed fully on movement and the present moment), while sunrise sessions involve a single continuous 40-minute sit.

years), and 2 priests (20+ years). Ages ranged from 21-60+, with 8 males (66.7%) and 4 females (33.3%), approximately mirroring the BZD's typical gender distribution (70-75% male). All participants identified as British, predominantly but not exclusively white. Only one participant reported a Buddhist upbringing, with 7 identifying as non-religious prior to Zen engagement, though this did not appear to determine the depth or character of their engagement with silence. Most described prior experience with contemplative practices, including mindfulness and other Buddhist-derived techniques. Educational backgrounds varied from no formal qualifications to doctoral-level study.

These demographic categories were selected to explore whether personal history, contemplative background, or length of practice shaped participants' relationships with silence. While the sample was relatively homogeneous in terms of ethnicity and nationality, it encompassed a range of spiritual orientations and meditation experience levels. Educational and gender diversity did not appear to shape participants' reported experiences in ways that were analytically distinct.

Although this sample does not capture the full diversity of the BZD community - such as visiting teachers from France and Japan, or practitioners from other ethnic backgrounds at different times - it offers a situated view of how silence was lived and shared during fieldwork. Where relevant, experiential variation by practice duration is developed in the following sections.

4.1.3 Quantitative Overview

The quantitative data reveals patterns in how participants experienced silence during zazen practice. **Table 1** summarises group-level mean scores for 7 dimensions of silent experience across practitioner categories.

Table1: Mean Ratings of Key Dimensions of Silence Experience Across Groups

Dimension	Newcomers (n=2)	Returning (n=3)	Ordained (n=5)	Priests (n=2)	Overall (n=12)
Comfort with silence	2	6.5	8.5	9	6.4
Sense of shared atmosphere	5.5	7.5	8.5	9.5	7.8
Feeling of connection to others	4.5	6	8	9	7
Contribution to group identity	3	6.5	8	9.5	7
Embodied awareness	4.5	7	8	8.5	7
Altered perception of time	4	7.5	8.5	8.5	7.2
Change in experience over time	N/A	8.5	8.5	9.5	8.7
Group Average	3.9	7.1	8.3	9.1	7.3

Note: This table summarises participants' average Likert scale ratings (1-10) across seven measures related to experiences of silence during group zazen practice. Results are presented by practitioner group, as well as overall. Higher scores indicate stronger reported experiences. Mean scores were calculated based on participant responses within each group. Individual participants rated each dimension on the 1-10 scale, with these individual ratings then averaged within each experience group. Where participants had no basis for response (e.g., newcomers rating change over time), scores are recorded as not applicable (N/A).

The Group Average row demonstrates a developmental progression from newcomers (3.9) to returning students (7.1) to ordained practitioners (8.3) to priests (9.1), indicating how engagement with silence deepens with experience. However, this should not be interpreted as a smooth or uniform trajectory; as explored in Section 4.2, newcomers reported intense, sometimes disorienting experiences of silence, showing its uneven accessibility. Three patterns in the data warrant particular attention:

1. The most dramatic differences between newcomers and experienced practitioners appear in “comfort with silence” (7-point difference) and “contribution to group identity” (6.5-point difference), suggesting these represent significant areas of transformation through practice.
2. While newcomers rated their “feeling of connection to others” relatively low (4.5), they rated their “sense of shared atmosphere” notably higher (5.5), indicating that even first-time practitioners perceive an atmospheric quality in shared silence before developing a sense of interpersonal connection.
3. The highest overall ratings were for “sense of shared atmosphere” (7.8) and “change in experience over time” (8.7), suggesting these dimensions become increasingly salient with continued engagement in zazen.

4.2 (1) Intersubjective Paradox of Connection in Silence

A central theme across participant accounts was the experience of feeling deeply connected to others while remaining immersed in private experience. This form of relationality challenges conventional understandings of intersubjectivity that presume shared meaning or verbal exchange as prerequisites for connection. While Group averages indicated a progressive increase in the ‘feeling of connection to others’ during group zazen based on experience level, with newcomers rating 4.5, returning participants 6, ordained members 8, and priests 9, for an overall average of 7 on a 10-point scale, this connection was often described paradoxically.

‘It is both a connected and deeply private practice’

This layered quality of presence was captured in a recurring description of zazen as aloneness but together. Matthew (ordained) explained: “It is both a connected and deeply private practice... You feel like you know the others without speaking.” Sarah (ordained) said: “I feel

a strong presence of the group, like we're all part of the same body of silence, yet I'm also within my own experience. It's like being alone together." These reflections illustrate a form of intersubjectivity that is not based on accessing others' thoughts, but on shared intentionality and embodied presence. Grace (ordained) offered a nuanced reflection that deepens this point: "There is a shared energy in the space... I have sat next to people before who appeared still, but I sometimes sensed unease." She clarified, however, that zazen teaches the importance of non-attachment to such impressions. Rather than a claim to know others' inner states, her reflection suggests a heightened sensitivity to embodied cues, held lightly within the ethical frame of practice. This recalls Merleau-Ponty's ([1945] 2012, p.432) notion of pre-reflective, embodied intersubjectivity, where the body is not merely a container for subjectivity but the very condition of relational experience. Grace further elaborated that: "You let go of judgement and that leads to a feeling of a shared existence... this affects us all the time, but zazen shows it to us." Her reflection aligns with Jackson's (1996) emphasis on intersubjective 'immediacy' - the already-present field of *being-with* that zazen helps reveal.

A Shared Atmospheric Presence

Many participants described an atmospheric quality to the shared silence, using terms like "energy," "field," and "presence" to articulate what they experienced. As Lily (returning student) explained: "It's not just an absence of sound but a presence that seems to fill the room. This shared field becomes more noticeable the longer I sit." This sense of a collective energetic field was particularly pronounced in larger group settings, as noted by Elliott, a long-term ordained practitioner: "Silence feels very powerful with large groups. Attending sesshin¹² can be very profound when silence falls with larger groups sharing in it." Another ordained practitioner, David, compared this phenomenon to an electrical circuit: "It's like being part of a battery that charges up with more people - the energy builds and sustains everyone's practice in a way that's difficult to replicate when sitting alone."

This relational awareness became visible through subtle acts of social attunement: when a practitioner coughed, sneezed or made some unintended sound, the individual would often bow slightly toward the wall with their hands pressed together - momentarily releasing the cosmic

¹² Sesshin (接心) is a Japanese Zen term that means 'to touch the heart-mind' or 'collecting the mind.' It refers to an intensive meditation retreat, usually lasting several days, held in silence and focused on extended periods of zazen, along with chanting, silent meals, work practice (samu), and dharma talks from teachers.

mudra to perform the gesture. Although most participants could not have visually perceived this, the act nonetheless seemed to address the room itself, signaling a recognition of others and an ethic of shared silence. These micro-gestures reflect a corporeal sensitivity to the ambient field of shared silence, a form of relational awareness that resonates with Schmitz's (2014) notion of atmospheres as spatially extended affective fields. Eisenlohr (2023), working from this neo-phenomenological lineage, emphasises how atmospheres in ritual settings do not merely envelop individuals but actively shape how rituals are felt and perceived. Through semiotic structures of indexicality and iconicity - co-presence and resemblance - ritual atmospheres become somatically persuasive (Cassaniti, 2024).

Within the dojo, silence becomes more than a discipline; it feels '*right*', '*shared*', and '*orderly*' - not through verbal agreement but through a felt sensory field. This speaks to participants' descriptions of a "shared discipline" or "energy in the room," which, though ineffable, affirmed both individual stillness and collective belonging. In this context, the bowing gesture may be understood as a form of quiet empathy - not emotional identification, but an embodied responsiveness to the shared atmosphere. It affirms mutual presence without requiring explicit recognition. Silence, then, emerges not as an isolated practice, but as a relational, atmospheric field sustained through intersubjective attunement, sensitivity, and tacit care.

Sonic Textures of Being

While certain participant narratives emphasised the emotional and mental dimensions of intersubjectivity, my sensory ethnography recorded its rich auditory texture: the collective rhythms of breathing, occasional fidgeting and adjustments of posture, sighs, and the unmistakable gurgling of stomachs collectively created what I recorded as "sonic textures of being." These bodily sounds, rather than disrupting the silence, seemed to humanise and authenticate it, creating a shared acoustic environment that acknowledged the physical reality of being without idealising it.

4.3 (2) Identity Formation Through Shared Practice

The quantitative data revealed that participants overall rated the contribution of silence to group identity 7/10, with a marked developmental trajectory from newcomers (3.0) to priests (9.5). This suggests that embodied silent practice can transform one's sense of belonging and relation

to others. One priest, Ren, articulated this process in terms of corporeal dissolution of boundaries:

Ego is let go of. Our personal identities soften through shared stillness, uniform posture, and collective silence. We return to a spacious awareness, where the illusion of separateness no longer holds. This is a meeting ground that transcends thought and, in turn, individual identity constructs.

The uniformity of posture creates what my fieldnotes described as “visible harmony despite invisible diversity”, a corporeal synchrony that enables a collective identity not dependent on verbal articulation or shared beliefs - an identity which, as Ren described, is “shared with all beings through asanga¹³, yet no words can touch it.”

This emergence of a shared identity through embodied practice, rather than discursive agreement, challenges conventional understanding of group formation. As Alistair (ordained) observed: “Silence makes us aware that we have a connection with others beyond verbal communications or direct exchanges.” This connection develops not through explicit social bonding but through what Elliot (ordained) described as “a sense of sharing a spacious awareness beyond our personal thoughts.” The emphasis here is not on likeness of mind or mutual understanding but on a shared mode of being - a collective inhabiting of what Hugh (returning student) called “a thundering silence.”

Nondual Identity

A recurring theme observed in more experienced participant accounts was how the discipline of collective silence helps dissolve judgments that typically shape social differentiation. As Elliot explained:

During the beginning of zazen, and particularly on retreats, I often notice I can be full of hard emotions directed at others. Deciding who to like and dislike, who is annoying, who is doing it wrong. After periods of practice these judgements quieten.

Elliot’s reflection suggests that silence functions as a kind of moral recalibration - a condition in which reactive habits of categorisation and evaluation are stripped away. This aligns with Schimmel’s (1975, p.255) account of spiritual discipline in Sufi traditions, particularly in “the way of Junayd,” where practices such as fasting, ritual purity, and sustained silence are

¹³ Ren’s use of the term “asanga” refers to the Sanskrit concept of non-attachment, associated with the 4th-century Buddhist philosopher Asanga. While not central to this study’s analytic framework, it reflects how more advanced practitioners often draw on lineage-based terms to express their experience of silent communion.

understood as necessary conditions for refining perception and cultivating ethical presence. In both contexts, silence can actively support a loosening of the egoic structures that sustain social judgment, allowing space for a different mode of relational being to emerge.

However, this process does not erase individual experience. As Matthew (ordained) noted, “everyone is experiencing their own private thoughts and energies. We practice surrendering to all that is, together, and to not resist what is.” Rather than negating personal awareness, the shared silence of zazen discloses a deeper stratum of co-presence, one typically obscured by social and cognitive habits of differentiation. This transformation aligns with Dōgen’s understanding of zazen as a practice that transcends dualistic thinking. For Dōgen, seated meditation is not a means to achieve enlightenment, but the direct embodiment of Buddha-nature - a “practice-realisation” in which the boundary between path and goal dissolves (Leighton, 2007, p.84). Within this non-dual framework, group identity does not form through fixed social categories but emerges as an ethical relationality in which distinctions between self and other become porous, an insight that reflects the immediate, shared ground of existence that zazen actualises.

4.4 (3) Altered Perceptions of Time During Zazen

The relationship between embodied practice and temporal experience emerged as a significant dimension across participant accounts. Experienced practitioners consistently reported that sustained silent sitting produced a distinctive shift in time perception, not merely slowing or accelerating subjective time, but fundamentally altering its texture and quality. As Sarah (ordained) explained: “By the second half of the sit, my awareness has usually expanded open. The bell often catches me by surprise - not because I’ve lost track of time, but because I’ve entered a different relationship with time altogether.” This reframing of time appeared to unfold alongside a shift in the embodied atmosphere of the room. However, this temporal fluidity was not universally experienced. For newcomers like Rupert, time stretched painfully: “It seemed like it was never going to end”, reporting a sense of temporal elongation marked by discomfort. This contrast shows how temporal experience in zazen may be mediated by practice development and embodied attunement.

My sensory ethnography captured how the space itself began to pulse with a shared rhythm that dissolved individual temporalities. The temporal recalibrations reported by more experienced zazen practitioners closely relate to Bergson's (1913) '*real duration*' (*durée réelle*), a mode of temporality that is lived, affective, and continuous, rather than segmented or quantified. Rather than marking time in units or sequences, experienced practitioners described a shift into a fluid and immersive temporal field, especially following *kinhin*. This was not a withdrawal from time, but an intensification of its felt quality. Such experiences suggest that zazen cultivates a form of durational attunement, in which time is not measured but inhabited, not external to the body, but coursing through it. This shared duration was irreducible to any clock, yet experientially real in its intersubjective force.

4.5 (4) Impacts of Silence Beyond the Dojo

While the primary setting for silence in this study was the BZD, participants repeatedly emphasised that its effects were not confined to formal practice. In response to an open-ended question about whether silence had influenced their relationships beyond the dojo, many participants described how the discipline had shaped their orientation to everyday life - emotionally, relationally, and perceptually.

Rachael (ordained) reflected: "I relish silence, and if I don't have it for a while, it becomes noticeable", indicating a shift from experiencing silence as a meditative tool to valuing it as a life necessity. She also observed that when she hasn't been practicing silence, simple life scenarios can quickly become irritating, suggesting that regular zazen supports a less reactive stance toward life beyond the dojo. Similarly, Lily (returning student) described how silence changed her way of relating to others: "I suspect I act on anger or sadness much less than I would otherwise... I am a better listener when regularly practicing zazen." These reflections point to an increasing sensitivity to the emotional and social fabric of everyday interactions. As Csordas (1993) suggests, embodied practices can recalibrate how attention is structured, shaping not only what one notices, but how one relates to it. In this sense, silence becomes not merely a technique but an ongoing disposition, subtly shaping interpersonal awareness and emotional regulation beyond the ritual setting (Cassaniti, 2024).

4.6 (5) The Distinctive Experiences of Newcomers

For newcomers, the dojo environment represented an unfamiliar sensory and social landscape that demanded immediate adaptation. While the deeper sense of group identity develops over time (as indicated by the quantitative findings in **Table 1**), newcomers nonetheless perceived certain atmospheric qualities of shared silence. Kieran, a first-time practitioner, described this paradoxical experience:

I didn't feel that connected to others, yet there were times I did feel like this experience was shared... The silence means people's individual identities feel less important. It felt like there is a quality in the room through the silence, a shared discipline.

This observation helps explain why the newcomers rated “sense of shared atmosphere” (5.5) notably higher than “contribution to group identity” (3.0) and “feeling of connection to others” (4.5). Kieran also described a heightened self-consciousness: “At first, I felt self-conscious, wondering if I was doing it right, if I was shifting too much, but after a while, I started paying more attention to my breath instead of worrying about others.” His experience shows how initial encounters with zazen are often mediated through social comparison and performance anxiety rather than through direct engagement with the practice itself.

As discussed in 4.4, Rupert experienced time as painfully elongated. He further described the overall experience as “living hell. I just wanted to get up and leave most of the time. The silence felt overwhelming... my mind was racing.” During this sit, his physical stillness lasted less than 5 minutes before restlessness compelled him to repeatedly stand, stretch, and adjust his posture throughout the session. Though the room was cool, he reported feeling increasingly overheated, attributing this to his growing agitation. Such reactions show that the intersubjective potential of silence is not universally accessible; for some, silence exposes inner turbulence rather than mutual presence. While such discomfort is often associated with newcomers to meditation, this research revealed that even experienced practitioners can encounter similar struggles, particularly during periods of distance from regular practice. The agitation Rupert experienced represents a common challenge that can manifest both within and beyond formal dojo settings (as we have seen with Rachael's account in 4.5, and Elliot's revelation of bound up “hard emotions” towards others in 4.3) suggesting that one's relationship with silence remains dynamic rather than static.

Over the course of fieldwork, I was increasingly assigned to sit beside newcomers as my experience grew. Through this proximity, I became sensitised to the fidgeting, sighing, and shifting often observable among those newer to zazen. This contrasted sharply with the somatic quietude I typically experienced when seated beside more regular, longer-term practitioners. However, while the analysis here draws primarily on findings from the 2 newcomers who formally participated in the study, my field observations included several other first-time practitioners who expressed similar discomforts during informal post-sitting conversations. These broader accounts suggest that Kieran and Rupert's responses reflect common rather than idiosyncratic reactions to initial zazen practice. This was further reinforced through my sensory ethnography, which followed Pink's ([2009] 2015, p.63) model of *sensory emplaced learning* as a way of understanding how meaning is generated through the body's situated and multisensory engagement within a particular environment.

Beyond Discomfort

Despite these challenges, both newcomers reported brief moments of intersubjective attunement that gave them a taste of what zazen silence might offer beyond their initial discomfort. Rupert said:

There were very brief moments when I stopped fidgeting and thinking about how I could ethically escape... I could feel there was a sacredness in the room. It stood out because during those moments everything felt very still and intentional.

This suggests a nascent capacity to attune to the shared atmosphere of the dojo. Crucially, during his interview, Rupert did not describe this stillness as something he achieved through deliberate effort; instead, he explained that it emerged in the absence of striving (when he stopped trying to control his experience). This reflects the Daoist and Zen-inflected sensibility of *wu wei*, as discussed by Loy (1985, p.76), in which presence arises not through action but through non-interference. Rather than forcing calm, Rupert accessed this 'sacredness' by allowing his body to settle without resistance. Such "letting-be" points to a central principle in Zen: that openness and depth of awareness are not produced by effort, but become available when effort is relinquished (Ibid, p.76). This non-striving approach (*wu wei*) may seem counterintuitive to Western mindsets (Tannen, 1985) - steeped in high-achievement, high-verbal and goal orientated cultural norms - yet it reflects the core Zen understanding that our natural state of awareness is often obscured by our very attempts to attain it.

4.7 (6) Embodied Attunement as a Unifying Trajectory

While all participants described silence as a powerful sensory experience, their capacity to remain physically and mentally attuned showed mixed capabilities that generally followed a developmental progression. The quantitative data supports this trajectory in two complementary ways: “embodied awareness” shows a clear progression from newcomers (4.5) to priests (8.5), while “change in experience over time” reveals how practitioners themselves perceive this transformation, with consistently high ratings from returning students (8.5) to ordained practitioners (8.5) to priests (9.5). This growth was not simply cognitive or affective. Rather than merely changing thoughts about or emotional reactions to silence, zazen seemingly cultivated a transformation in how practitioners holistically inhabited their bodies.

This reflects what Csordas (1993) terms a *somatic mode of attention* - a bodily turning-toward the world. Drawing on Schutz (1967), Csordas asks: “What is the role of attention in the constitution of subjectivity and intersubjectivity as bodily phenomena?” and suggests that such turning-toward entails more bodily and multisensory engagement than is typically acknowledged in psychological accounts (Ibid, p.138). In zazen, this mode of embodied attentiveness is cultivated through stillness and silence, not as isolation, but as immersion in a shared relational field, where collective ‘spatial awareness’ as referred to by more advanced members, becomes a bodily *dwelling-with others*.

This is empirically illustrated by experienced practitioners’ descriptions of their evolving sensory and perceptual engagement. Certain experienced members of the community reported that sensations of discomfort and distraction eventually give way to a capacity to “enter inside the body” as Clive (ordained) put it, by “allowing thoughts to arise and pass without following them.” This was not simply physical endurance, but a qualitative transformation in perception. “Sometimes the mind makes a lot of noise, even if I’m completely still,” Clive continued, however:

Through surrendering to the now, you’re not pulled around by it. You feel the aliveness in the body...Thoughts aren’t neglected but accepted within the collective spacious awareness. This is peace.”

What is cultivated here is not stoic immobility, but somatic harmonisation, a quieting of bodily reactivity that enables deeper modes of relational presence between self and other. Both priests exemplified this attunement, as did all ordained participants and one returning student in this

study, describing in their own ways their experiences of oneness or the embodied non-duality during zazen - a felt sense of “eternality” as several participants noted, that is accessed through the “energy body” as Clive pinpointed, revealing an interrelated connectedness between “form and formlessness”.

4.8 Silent Epistemology

This research revealed a distinctive mode of knowing that emerges through shared contemplative silence, which I term silent epistemology. While Pagis's (2010) identification of silent intersubjectivity examines how meditation practitioners maintain shared social connections without verbal communication (see page 12), silent epistemology addresses a fundamentally different question: how silence functions as a vehicle for knowledge transmission and creation.

Where silent intersubjectivity explains how people share connection without words, silent epistemology examines how people know through silence - revealing forms of understanding that cannot be reduced to or replaced by discursive communication. Pagis (2010, p.3) describes how "covert mechanisms" are brought into play despite the absence of verbal exchange. While Pagis demonstrates that meditation practice involves important non-verbal intersubjective dimensions rather than being a purely individual pursuit, silent epistemology extends this insight by showing how these mechanisms generate embodied knowledge through transformative co-presence - building on Pagis's "embodied involvement" (Ibid, p.25) to establish a collective epistemological domain.

During my fieldwork, I often observed teachers intervening to break the silence with verbal guidance during zazen. Notably, these interventions followed a distinct pattern: they were rare during sunrise sessions, where only priests, ordained and returning members were present, but more common and frequent during sessions with more first-timers. Often consisting of simple phrases such as "come back", "return to the breath... return to the posture", "notice the body in space", "notice silence", or "let go of thought", these verbal cues acted affectively, where the collective atmosphere appeared to shift, grounding the collective back into the here and now.

What became apparent through my sensory ethnography was that the priests' ability to sense when to intervene - to detect the quality of collective attention - was itself a product of silence.

It was the silent field that made this knowing possible. When I questioned Ren (priest) about these patterns during his interview, rather than describing his vocalised interventions as cognitively determined, he explained that they arise through presence, not thought. He typically intervenes "when the silence becomes noisy - usually not with audible sound, but when the collective is generating a lot of mental noise." When pressed on how one could perceive silence as 'noisy' without audible cues, Ren explained that it is "something sensed, felt." This capacity to detect the quality of collective attention recalls the Japanese concept of *ishin-denshin* (以心伝心) - transmission from mind to mind (Bielefeldt, 1988, p. 5) - which arises not as an exception to silence, but as a capacity made intelligible through it.

Silas (priest) described breaking the silence in similar intuitive terms: "guiding the collective back to being present during zazen, this does not arise through thought... I couldn't say where it comes from, only that it arises intuitively through presence." One moment from my fieldnotes captured his quiet declaration during an unsettled session: "there is nowhere to go, nowhere to be, nothing to reach", redirecting the group back to the body. While these are vocal interventions, they did not function as argument or explanation. Rather, they produced an affective recalibration across the room - a gentle redirection akin to what Cassaniti (2024) refers to as "silent suasion": embodied persuasion that restructures shared space. Through such subtle interventions, silence revealed itself not as absence, but as a generative medium of transmission.

The concept of silent epistemology contributes to anthropology by challenging the discipline's longstanding privileging of language and representation as primary sites of cultural knowledge. Despite the sensory and embodied turns in anthropology, methodological emphasis continues to fall on what can be verbalised, recorded, and categorised. This research suggests that significant dimensions of social experience and cultural transmission occur through non-verbal modes that require alternative forms of ethnographic attention (Dragojlovic & Samuels, 2021; Pagis, 2010). By documenting how affective attunement functions as a mode of social coordination and collective experience during zazen, this study bridges phenomenological approaches to embodiment with broader questions of social formation and ethical cultivation.

Beyond anthropology, this research contributes to contemplative studies by showing how shared silence creates not just individual transformation but collective fields of experience that transcend conventional subject-object distinctions (Schmitz et al, 2011). While scholars like

Pagis (2010) have theorised silent intersubjectivity, and Cassaniti (2024) has analysed embodied persuasion through silence, this study reframes silence not as a passive backdrop but as an active condition through which situated knowledge emerges and circulates atmospherically, beyond “subjectivist interiority” (Eisenlohr, 2023, p.37) - a perspective that challenges Western logocentric traditions and invites new modes of theorising relationality and transmission beyond discourse.

5. Limitations and Future Research

This study was limited by a relatively small and demographically homogeneous sample - predominantly male, white, and British - which may narrow the interpretive range of silence across cultural and gendered lines. While reflective of the BZD’s usual composition, future research could engage more diverse Zen communities, including visiting international teachers. Although gendered dynamics were not the focus here, future work could examine whether male-dominated spaces mediate comfort, presence, or perceived authority in silent practice differently.

The dojo’s indoor setting may have also shaped how silence was experienced; contemplative practices in outdoor or natural environments may reveal different affective textures and intersubjective dynamics. Feld’s (1996) work on acoustemology - how sound mediates embodied relationships to place - offers a useful frame for considering how environmental embeddedness can shape sensory and relational experience. Although this study focused primarily on silence, ritual sound elements such as the han (wooden sounding board), keisu (metal bowl bell), and taiko (ritual drum) were integral to the affective rhythm of zazen. While not analytically foregrounded in this work, these instruments shaped the sonic and atmospheric landscape of the dojo and may have contributed to collective attunement in ways that intersect with, rather than oppose, silence. Finally, future studies might include longitudinal, cross-traditional, or co-ethnographic approaches to further explore silent epistemologies across varied spatial, cultural, and ritual contexts.

6. Conclusions

This dissertation set out to explore how silence facilitates intersubjective experience among zazen practitioners, how it shapes relational identity through embodied practice, and how

ethnographic engagement with contemplative silence can challenge logocentric understandings of sociality. While Pagis (2010) offers a pivotal reframing of meditative silence as relational and embodied, and Cassaniti (2024) explores ‘silent suasions’ in interpersonal mediation, the concept of silent epistemology, drawn from both Zen sources and anthropological frameworks, goes further by framing silence not only as a mode of relating, but as a medium of knowing.

These findings supported the emergence of a shared atmosphere in which practitioners can feel connected without verbal language. More than enabling communal identity in a conventional sense, silence played a central role in dissolving ego-bound identities and cultivating a relational, embodied, and fluid form of belonging shaped through posture, discipline, and stillness. In this context, identity is not asserted but softened. Three further themes emerged beyond the initial research questions: the temporal transformations of zazen, the impacts of silence on everyday life, and the distinctive sensory experiences of newcomers, requiring further investigation. Together, these insights call for an anthropology that listens differently - one that recognises silence not as absence, but as an ethical, relational, and epistemic force.

Appendices

Appendix A: Recruitment Poster

Research on Silence in Zazen Meditation

Conducted by: Nicholas Watkins, *University of Bristol, Anthropology & Archaeology Department*

Hello my name is Nicholas. I am a student at the University of Bristol conducting research for my BA dissertation project. My research is examining how silence in zazen meditation functions as a potential intersubjective bridge, creating opportunities for deeper interpersonal understanding and connection among practitioners. It also extends to engage with the wider field of consciousness research, exploring how shared silent experiences might contribute to our understanding of collective awareness and perception.

What I'm Doing

- Participating and observing the functions of zazen practice to understand the role of silence.
- Collecting data from practitioners through questionnaires and interviews (if you're interested in sharing your thoughts, let me know!).
- Respecting the space, practices, and traditions of the dojo.

Why This Research?

Zazen meditation offers a unique context to study how silence shapes intersubjective experiences, embodiment, and identity constructs. Your insights and participation could help deepen our understanding of this practice.

Your Privacy and Ethics

- My research follows the ethical guidelines of the University of Bristol.
- Participation is entirely voluntary.
- All shared information will be treated with respect and confidentiality.

How to Get Involved

If you are interested in learning more about my project or sharing your experiences, please feel free to:

- Speak to me after practice.
- Email me: Confidential or WhatsApp: Confidential

Thank You!

I deeply appreciate your support and the opportunity to learn from this community.

Please feel free to reach out with any questions or concerns.

Appendix B: Questionnaire

Section 1. Background

1. How long have you been practicing zazen?
2. Do you identify with any religious or spiritual tradition? (Optional). *If you feel comfortable*, you may also share anything about your background that you feel shapes how you relate to silence or group meditation.
3. How often do you attend group meditation sessions?
4. What motivated you to start zazen?
5. Do you primarily meditate alone, in groups, or both?

Section 2. Silence and Intersubjectivity

6. How connected do you feel to others during group zazen meditation? (Rate from 1-10, where 1 is not at all connected and 10 is deeply connected.)
7. Can you describe what contributes to this sense of connection or disconnection for you?
8. Do you feel that the shared silence enhances your understanding of others in the group?
9. Can you describe how this understanding manifests for you?

For example, do you feel you can sense others' emotional states or presence?

Does it create a feeling of mutual interconnectedness that is sensed beyond yourself? If so, what senses are engaged for you to acknowledge others?

10. If you feel it does not, is there anything that you feel may prevent you from connecting to others during zazen?
11. In your experience, does silence create a shared atmosphere in the room during group meditation? (Rate from 1-10, where 1 is no shared atmosphere and 10 is a deeply unified atmosphere)
12. Can you recall a specific moment when the group silence felt particularly meaningful?

Section 3. Silence and Group Identity

13. Do you feel that practicing silence with others contributes to a sense of group identity?
(Rate from 1-10, where 1 is no contribution and 10 is a strong contribution)
14. How would you describe the role of silence in shaping your relationship with the group?
- For example: Do you feel that silence helps you connect with others on a deeper level?
 - Does the shared silence create a sense of unity or equality among group members?
 - Does the silence affect your perception of the group as a community?
 - Do you feel more comfortable or closer to the group during silent meditation compared to other forms of interaction?
15. Do you think silence creates a sense of equality among practitioners, regardless of experience level?
16. In your opinion, how does group silence differ when practiced with experienced practitioners versus new practitioners? (*Leave blank if you have just begun practicing zazen*)
17. How important do you think shared silence is in creating a sense of belonging in the group?

Section 4. Silence as Embodied Practice

18. How aware do you feel of physical sensations in your body during zazen? (Rate from 1-10, where 1 is hardly notice my body and 10 is highly attuned to physical sensations)
19. Which of the following best describes how silence affects your physical and sensory awareness? (*Select all that apply*)
- I become more aware of my breath.
 - I notice physical sensations (e.g., tension, relaxation).
 - My sense of hearing becomes heightened.
 - Other (please specify):

20. Do you feel a sense of stillness or movement within your body?
21. How do you perceive your thoughts and emotions during silent meditation?
22. Do you ever find silence during zazen challenging or uncomfortable? (rate from 1-10, where 1 is extremely uncomfortable, and 10 is always comfortable).
(Optional: Please elaborate if you'd like)
23. Can you describe any shifts in your sense of self or relationships that you can attribute with silent meditation? *-Leave blank if this was your first sitting*

Section 5. Temporal Changes and Reflection

24. Has your experience with silence during zazen changed over time? (Rate from 1–10, where 1 is no change and 10 is significant change) - *Leave blank if this was your first meditation*
25. If it has changed, how would you describe that change? - *Leave blank if this was your first sitting*
26. How differently do you perceive time during zazen compared to everyday experience? (Rate from 1-10, where 1 is no difference and 10 is completely altered perception of time)
27. Do you think silence in zazen has influenced how you relate to silence (and noise) over time?
28. Has silence had influences in your life and relationships with others beyond the Bristol Zen Dojo? *-Leave blank if this was your first sitting*

Section 6. Closing Reflection

29. In one sentence, how would you summarise what silence means to you in the context of zazen?
30. Is there anything else you would like to share about your experiences with silence and zazen meditation?

Silent Epistemology: Embodied Intersubjectivity in Zazen

Invitation

You are being invited to take part in a research project. Prior to making your decision as to whether you would like to participate, it is important for you to understand why the research is being conducted and what your participation will involve. Please consider the following information and take your time to read carefully and discuss with others if you wish. Please also ask me if there is anything that appears unclear to you, or if you would like more information on anything. Please take your time to decide whether you wish to take part. Thank you.

Research Outline and Ethical Considerations:

This study explores how silence shapes individual and collective experiences during zazen meditation. Specifically, it examines how silence may facilitate a sense of connection between practitioners and influence their perceptions of self and others.

My study involves ethnographic participant observation to explore the role of silence in zazen meditation. As a researcher, I will be engaging in meditation sessions alongside practitioners in a nonintrusive manner, observing how silence is experienced within the shared practice. General observation of the meditation setting does not require individual consent, as no identifiable personal data will be collected from those who are simply present in the space.

If you choose to participate more actively - such as by completing a questionnaire, taking part in a formal interview, or providing in-depth personal reflections - written informed consent will be required. Informal conversations or remarks shared in communal spaces may be used in a generalised and anonymised way to inform contextual understanding, in line with the Association of Social Anthropologists (ASA) ethical guidelines. These will never be quoted or attributed without explicit permission. If you decide to take part in these discussions, you will be provided with full information about how your insights will be used. In terms of how the data is collected, the majority of data will be drawn from questionnaires and interviews to better understand experiences of silence and its role in this practice. The research is being conducted as part of my dissertation for a BA degree and is part of a broader academic

project exploring silence as a meaningful and relational practice. This study not only challenges logocentric paradigms that prioritise speech over silence but also contributes to a growing body of literature that situates nonduality as a lived and shared experience. By examining the interplay between silence, sensory intersubjectivity, and the collective practice of zazen, this research sheds light on how meditation creates conditions for transcending dualistic modes of being and understanding.

Why have I been invited to participate?

You were chosen to participate in the research project as you are over the age of 13 and you have participated in a zazen session today. A total of 12 individuals will be participating in this study.

Do I have to take part?

Taking part in this study is entirely voluntary. It is your decision whether you want to be included. I will describe the study and go through this information sheet with you prior to your participation, whilst answering any questions you may have. If you decide to participate, I will proceed with asking you to sign a consent form to ensure you have understood the process for this research. Whilst your personal data can be anonymised, once the data relating to the research questions has been drawn into results, it will not be possible to withdraw this data. The cut-off-period for the withdrawal process is due to the hand in date of my dissertation. The final date for withdrawing the said information will be: 01/04/2025.

What will happen to me if I take part and what will I have to do?

You will be invited to complete a questionnaire and participate in a follow up interview (prearranged to suit your schedule). These will focus on your experiences with zazen meditation, particularly your interpretations and sensory experiences of silence, both individually and as part of a group. The interview could last anywhere from 15 minutes to 1 hour. Please inform me if at any stage you feel uncomfortable with any topic question and would prefer to skip to the next question.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks involved in taking part in the project?

The risks or possible disadvantages of participating in this project are close to none.

However, for some individuals, particularly when first starting zazen, uncomfortable or challenging streams of thought may arise initiating feelings of discomfort and sensitivity. It is within my ethical moral code as a person, as well as abiding to the University of Bristol's ethical codes to do no harm, and not to impact a person's well-being in any way that could be considered negative. Essentially, you hold the power of making the conscious decision as to what you choose to share with me.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

This study seeks to contribute towards the spread of knowledge regarding the intersubjective elements of silence through zazen. Therefore, the primary benefit of participating in this study is that your experiences and data may assist others in becoming more informed about the practice, as well as contributing to dissolving cultural indifferences around silence, particularly in Western societies. Participative contributions will be compiled within the archive of this field of research, which collectively contributes towards our active involvement and understanding of how silence may be a key modulator for deeper relationality in societies.

Will my participation in this project be kept confidential?

- Any sensitive data stored about an identifiable person, or data classified as confidential will be stored securely on an encrypted, secure, password protected, University of Bristol system during and after the study. Importantly, anonymising your data involves taking away any means of identifying you from it. However, any information deemed as confidential simply will not be shared.
- The data for this research will be collected through non-audio recorded interviews, collection of questionnaires from participants, as well as documentations of written fieldnotes.
- The primary reason for anonymising data is to protect individuals' privacy upon making the data resources available that activities such as research and planning rely on. In this case, your printed name and signature are required for you to participate in this research. Under the Data Protection Act 1998 (DPA), it remains legitimate to use personal data for certain purposes. However, when the research is submitted, your name within the paper itself can be anonymised. This would be achieved by replacing

any names with a 'code' that cannot be traced back to you, e.g. A111. Therefore, your personal identity data will remain protected when the research is submitted.

Importantly, the data you have given that will be drawn into the results of the study ultimately will not amount to a disclosure of your personal data.

Who has access to your data?

The data.bris University of Bristol Research Data repository holds data generated by activities conducted by its academic researches. Whilst the vast majority of our datasets are 'Open', with access requiring no registration, in some instances, for example, research participants would prefer their data to be stored in our restricted dataset, where data is made available only to approved bona fide researchers only, whereby their host institution has signed a Research data access agreement for restricted data. However, there is a third option, designed for those who have not given explicit consent to share Open data. Requests for Controlled data must go through an appropriate Access committee (DAC) for approval, prior to data becoming sharable with bona fide researchers.

Data Disposal

All electronic information under the University of Bristol Disposal of Data policy ensures secure deletion or that it is otherwise rendered inaccessible before leaving the University. What does this mean in essence? All your personal data will be destroyed after I have completed the degree.

What will happen to the results of the research project?

Often, participants will want to know about the results of the study they have been involved in. If you would like for me to send you a copy of my full dissertation, I would be happy to do so. Depending initially on the results of the study and if the dissertation is deemed publishable, the research could be released to a wider audience. However, it is important to re-instate here, you will not be identified as a named individual in any report/publication, unless you have given your full consent.

Who has reviewed the study?

University of Bristol: Anthropology and Archaeology Department.

Further information and contact details

If you have any questions regarding anything we have discussed at any time, please do not hesitate to

contact me.

Name: Nicholas J Watkins

Phone: Confidential

Email: Confidential

Department of Anthropology and Archaeology

CONSENT FORM

Silent Epistemology: Embodied Intersubjectivity in Zazen

Brief Project Outline:

This project aims to investigate the role of silence in zazen meditation, focusing on its function as a medium for individual and collective experiences. By focusing on silence as a shared and embodied practice, the study seeks to challenge Western assumptions of silence as passive or isolating, positioning it instead as a dynamic force that shapes identity, connection, and social interaction. This work aims to contribute to anthropological and interdisciplinary understandings of silence as a meaningful practice, both within and beyond meditative contexts.

Do I have to take part?

Participation is entirely voluntary.

Can I withdraw at any time?

Yes, you can withdraw any at stage without a reason. However, should you later decide you want to withdraw after the results of the study have been drawn, and ultimately once the data has been anonymised, it is not possible for your data to be withdrawn.

What do I have to do?

You will be asked some questions, all of which will be based around zazen. If you can provide as detailed and accurate responses as you can, this will help the overall efficacy and depth of the study when generating the results.

How will the findings be used?

Whilst the overall nature of this research is qualitative - focusing on collecting and analysing nonnumerical data such as fieldnotes and notes from interviews to explore new or recurring experiences, concepts, and opinions - this study also incorporates a quantitative dimension. Participants' numerical ratings from questionnaires will be statistically analysed to complement and support the qualitative findings. The data and findings will be presented in relation to key themes and compared with similar findings within the existing literature. Additionally, the study will consider how transferable its insights are to other settings. For information regarding what happens to the data itself, please refer to the details provided on the previous page.

Will my taking part in the study be kept confidential?

Any confidential information will only be known by the investigators of this study. Therefore, the identity of anyone participating in this study who wishes to remain anonymous shall remain so.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

The risks or possible disadvantages of participating in this project are close to none. However, for some individuals, particularly when first starting zazen, uncomfortable or challenging streams of thought may arise. It is within my ethical and moral code as a person, as well as abiding to the University of Bristol's ethical codes to do no harm, and not to impact an individual's well-being in any way that could be considered negative. Essentially, you hold the power of making the conscious decision as to what you do choose to share with me.

What will happen to the data collected?

The data.bris University of Bristol Research Data repository holds data generated by activities conducted by its academic researches. Whilst the vast majority of our datasets are

‘Open’, with access requiring no registration, in some instances, for example, research participants would prefer their data to be stored in our restricted dataset, where data is made available only to approved bona fide researchers only, whereby their host institution has signed a Research data access agreement for restricted data. However, there is a third option, designed for those who have not given explicit consent to share Open data. Requests for Controlled data must go through an appropriate Access committee (DAC) for approval, prior to data becoming sharable with bona fide researchers. All electronic information under the University of Bristol Disposal of Data policy ensures secure deletion or that it is otherwise rendered inaccessible before leaving the University. What does this mean in essence? All your personal data will be destroyed after I have completed the degree.

Please answer the following questions to the best of your knowledge

HAVE YOU:

- been given information explaining about the study? YES/ NO
- had an opportunity to ask questions and discuss this study? YES/ NO
- received satisfactory answers to all questions you asked? YES/ NO
- received enough information about the study for you to make a decision about your participation? YES/ NO

DO YOU UNDERSTAND:

That you are free to withdraw from the study and free to withdraw your data prior to final consent

- at any time?
- without having to give a reason for withdrawing?

I hereby fully and freely consent to my participation in this study

SIGNED _____ DATE _____

Name (printed): _____

If you have any concerns related to your participation in this study please direct them to the Faculty of Arts Research Ethics Committee/ Research Governance and Ethics Officer.

Appendix D: Interview schedule

1. **Can you tell me about your experience with zazen meditation?**
2. **What initially drew you to zazen practice?**
 - "Was there a specific moment or idea that inspired you to try zazen?"
 - "Did you have any expectations before starting? How do they compare to your current experience?"

Silence and Intersubjectivity

3. **In what ways do you feel connected to others during silent meditation?**
 - "Do you notice a sense of awareness of others while meditating in silence? What does that feel like?"
 - "Do you feel the group's presence enhances or diminishes your practice? Why?"
4. **How does silence in the group setting affect your experience of the practice?**
 - "Do you notice a difference in how you feel when meditating alone versus in a group? Could you describe that?"
 - "Does the silence in the group create any particular feelings or thoughts for you?"

Group Identity and Time

5. **Do you think silence plays a role in shaping the identity of the group? How so?**
 - "Do you feel the group would be different if silence wasn't a part of the practice? In what ways?"
 - "How does the shared silence contribute to your sense of being part of the group?"
6. **How would you describe the collective experience of silence during zazen?**
 - "Does the silence feel like something you share with others, or is it more of an individual experience for you?"
 - "Can you describe the atmosphere in the room during silent meditation? How does it make you feel?"
7. **How do you experience time during zazen compared to your everyday experience?**

Embodiment and Personal Impact

8. How does silence during zazen affect your sense of self?

- "Do you feel differently about yourself during silent meditation compared to other times? If so, how?"
- "Do you notice any changes in your thoughts, emotions, or physical sensations during silence?"

9. Do you feel that silence has influenced any other areas of your life? If so, how?

- "Have you noticed any changes in how you interact with others outside the Dojo?"
- "Has silence helped you in any personal, social, or professional contexts?"

Closing:

10. Is there anything else about your experience of zazen and silence that you would like to share?

- "was/ is there a memorable or impactful experience you've had with silence in zazen?"
- "Is there anything we haven't discussed that you think is important to share?"

11. Do you have any reflections on how silence has changed or impacted you over time? (N/A for newcomers)

- "If you look back to when you first started zazen, how has your relationship with silence evolved?"

Appendix E: Expert interview schedule (priests)

Section 1: How does silence facilitate intersubjective experiences among zazen practitioners within a shared meditation space.

1. In your observation, how do practitioners interact with silence?
2. Have you noticed any shared experiences or reactions among practitioners that seem to emerge from these silent periods?
3. How do you think silence impacts the collective energy or atmosphere in the room?
4. I have observed that teachers sometimes break the silence during zazen with verbal guidance. Could you elaborate on when you feel it's appropriate to intervene in this way, and for what purpose?

Section 2: What role does silence play in constructing or reshaping group identity during zazen practice.

5. In what ways do you believe silence helps to define the identity of your meditation group?
6. Can you share any observations on how newcomers adapt to the silent practices here compared to the more experienced sitters?
7. How is silence discussed or taught within your community, and how does this influence the group's cohesion or sense of belonging?

Section 3: In what ways do zazen practitioners experience and interpret silence as an embodied practice, and how does this influence their sense of self and other.

8. How do you personally interpret the role of silence in your meditation practice?

9. Could you share any memorable insights into how practitioners have described personal transformations or realisations that have occurred through engaging with silence?

10. Have you observed any common challenges or difficulties that practitioners face with silence?

11. How do you experience time during zazen, and what have other practitioners reported about their experiences during zazen, in comparison to time passing outside of meditation?

Final question:

12. Are there any teachings or philosophies that you emphasise to help practitioners integrate the practice of silence?

Bibliography:

Association of Social Anthropologists (2021). *ASA Ethical Guidelines 2021*. Available at: <https://www.theasa.org/ethics/> (Accessed: 14 April 2025).

Bauman, R. (1985). *Let Your Words Be Few: Symbolism of Speaking and Silence among Seventeenth-Century Quakers*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

Behar, R. (1996). *The Vulnerable Observer: Anthropology That Breaks Your Heart*. Boston: Beacon Press.

Berkovich-Ohana, A., Dor-Ziderman, Y., Glicksohn, J., & Goldstein, A. (2013). Alterations in the sense of time, space, and body in the mindfulness-trained brain: a neurophenomenologically-guided MEG study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 4, 912.

Bergson, H. (1913). *Time and Free Will: An Essay on the Immediate Data of Consciousness*. London: George Allen & Company.

Bernard, H.R. (2011). *Research Methods in Anthropology: Qualitative and Quantitative Approaches*. 5th ed. Lanham, MD: AltaMira Press.

Bielefeldt, C. (1988). *Dogen's Manuals of Zen Meditation*. Berkeley: University of California Press.

Bogner, A., and Menz, W. (2009). The theory-generating expert interview: Epistemological Interest, forms of knowledge, interaction. In A. Bogner, B. Littig, & W. Menz (Eds.), *Interviewing experts* (pp. 43–80). Palgrave Macmillan UK.

Boone, H.N. Jr. and Boone, D.A. (2012). Analyzing Likert data. *Journal of Extension*, 50(2), Article 2TOT2.

Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology, *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), pp. 77–101.

Casey, M. (2005). *Strangers to the City: Reflections on the Beliefs and Values of the Rule of St. Benedict*. Brewster, MA: Paraclete Press.

- Cassaniti, J. (2024). Silent suasions: interpersonal mediation in Thai meditation. *Journal of the Royal Anthropological Institute*, 30(1). pp. 61-76
- Clifford, J. and Marcus, G.E. (1986). *Writing Culture: The Poetics and Politics of Ethnography*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Creswell, J.W. and Plano Clark, V.L., (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. 3rd ed. Thousand Oaks, CA: SAGE Publications.
- Csordas, T.J. (1990). Embodiment as a paradigm for anthropology. *Ethos*, 18(1), pp. 5–47.
- Csordas, T.J. (1993). Somatic modes of attention, *Cultural Anthropology*, 8(2), pp. 135–156.
- Csordas, T. (1994). *Embodiment and experience: the existential ground of culture and self*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Das, V. (2007). *Life and Words: Violence and the Descent into the Ordinary*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Dauenhauer, B.P. (1980). *Silence: The Phenomenon and Its Ontological Significance*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Derrida, J. (1976). *Of Grammatology*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press.
- Dōgen, E. (2007). *Shōbōgenzō: The True Dharma-Eye Treasury*, Volume I. Translated by G. Nishijima and C. Cross. Berkeley: Numata Center for Buddhist Translation and Research.
- Dragojlovic, A.E.N. and Samuels, A. (2021). Tracing silences: Towards an anthropology of the unspoken and unspeakable. *History and Anthropology*, 32(4), pp.487-499.
- Eisenlohr, P. (2023). Atmospheres: The multisensoriality of spatially extended emotions *American Anthropological Association*, 50(1), pp. 37-50.
- Feld, S. (1996). Waterfalls of Song: An Acoustemology of Place Resounding in Bosavi, Papua New Guinea. In: Feld, S. and Basso, K.H. (eds.) *Senses of Place*. Santa Fe: School of American Research Press, pp. 91-135.
- Flick, U. (2014). *An introduction to qualitative research*. Edition 5. Los Angeles: Sage.

- Foucault, M. (1978). *The History of Sexuality, Volume 1: An Introduction*. New York: Pantheon Books.
- Glenn, C. (2004). *Unspoken: A Rhetoric of Silence*. Carbondale: Southern Illinois University Press.
- Guest, G., Bunce, A., and Johnson, L. (2006). How Many Interviews Are Enough? An Experiment with Data Saturation and Variability. *Field Methods*, 18(1), 59-82.
- Gurevitch, Z.D. (1989). Distance and Conversation. *Symbolic Interaction*, 12(2), pp. 251-263.
- Hammersley, M. and Atkinson, P. (2019). *Ethnography: Principles in Practice*. 4th ed. London: Routledge.
- Heine, S. (2023). Zen Body, Zen Mind: Dōgen's Approach to Meditation and Monastic Training. In: Heine, S. (ed.) *Readings of Dōgen's Treasury of the True Dharma Eye*. Leiden: Brill, pp. 63–78.
- Howes, D. (2003). *Sensual Relations: Engaging the Senses in Culture and Social Theory*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press.
- Jackson, M. (1996). *Things As They Are: New Directions in Phenomenological Anthropology*. Washington, D.C.: Georgetown University Press.
- Jaworski, A. (1993). *The Power of Silence: Social and Pragmatic Perspectives*. Newbury Park: Sage.
- Jule, A. (2004). *Gender, Participation and Silence in the Language Classroom: Sh-Shushing the Girls*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Komjathy, L. (2018). *Introducing Contemplative Studies*. Chichester: Wiley-Blackwell.
- Lebra, T.S. (1976). *Japanese Patterns of Behavior*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press.
- Leighton, T. D. (2007). *Visions of Awakening Space and Time: Dōgen and the Lotus Sutra*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Loy, D. (1985). Wei-Wu-Wei: Nondual Action. *Philosophy East and West*, 35(1), pp. 73-86.

- Mann, T. (1967). *The Magic Mountain*. Translated by H.T. Lowe-Porter. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Merleau-Ponty, M. ([1945] 2012). *Phenomenology of Perception*. Translated by D.A. Landes. London: Routledge.
- Nakane, I. (2007). *Silence in Intercultural Communication: Perceptions and Performance*. Amsterdam: John Benjamins.
- Pagis, M. (2009). Embodied self-reflexivity. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 73(3), pp. 265-283.
- Pagis, M. (2010). Producing Intersubjectivity in Silence: An Ethnographic Study of Meditation Practice. *Ethnography*, 33(4), 11(2):309-328
- Pagis, M. (2019). *Inward: Vipassana Meditation and the Embodiment of the Self*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Petkova, D.P. (2015). Beyond silence: A cross-cultural comparison between Finnish 'quietude' and Japanese 'tranquillity'. *Eastern Academic Journal*, 4, pp.1–14.
- Pink, S. ([2009] 2015). *Doing Sensory Ethnography*. 2nd ed. London: Sage.
- Preston, D.L. (1988). *The Social Organisation of Zen Practice: Constructing Transcultural Reality*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Ricoeur, P. (1979). The function of fiction in shaping reality. *Man and World*, 12(2), pp. 123-141.
- Schimmel, A. (1975). *Mystical Dimensions of Islam*. Chapel Hill: University of North Carolina Press.
- Schmitz, H., Müllan, R.O., & Slaby, J. (2011). Emotions outside the box - the new phenomenology of feeling and corporeality. *Phenomenology and the Cognitive Sciences*, 10(2), pp. 241-259.

- Schutz, A. (1967). *The Phenomenology of the Social World*. Evanston: Northwestern University Press.
- Sharma, A. (2004). *Hinduism as a Missionary Religion*. Waterloo: Wilfrid Laurier University Press.
- Simmel, G. (1906). The Sociology of Secrecy and of Secret Societies. *American Journal of Sociology*, 11(4), pp. 441-498.
- Spivak, G.C. (1988). Can the Subaltern Speak? In: Nelson, C. and Grossberg, L. (eds.) *Marxism and the Interpretation of Culture*. Urbana: University of Illinois Press, pp. 271-313.
- Stewart, K. (2011). Atmospheric attunements. *Environment and Planning D: Society and Space*, 29(3), pp. 445-453.
- Sudnow, D. (1978). *Ways of the Hand: The Organisation of Improvised Conduct*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Tannen, D. (1985). Silence: Anything But. In: Tannen, D. and Saville-Troike, M. (eds.) *Perspectives on Silence*. Norwood: Ablex, pp. 93-111.
- Wright, D.S. (1998). *Philosophical Meditations on Zen Buddhism*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Wright, D.S. (2008). Introduction: Rethinking Ritual Practice in Zen Buddhism. In: Heine, S. and Wright, D.S. (eds.) *Zen Ritual: Studies of Zen Buddhist Theory in Practice*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 3-19.
- Zerubavel, E. (2006). *The Elephant in the Room: Silence and Denial in Everyday Life*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.